

Periodate as an Analytical Reagent. Part IX. Determination of Sulphur Compounds Through Iodate Formed in the Reaction.

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Sulphide, hydrosulphide, sulphite, bisulphite, thiosulphate, trithionate and tetrathionate have been oxidised by metaperiodate under suitable conditions and determined by titrating the iodate formed in the reaction iodometrically after masking of the excess metaperiodate with molybdate.

PERIODATE¹ had been used as an oxidant for the determination of sulphide, hydrosulphide, sulphite, bisulphite, thiosulphate, trithionate and tetrathionate under the conditions where periodate is reduced to iodate stage only. The estimations were completed by titrating the excess of periodate. It would be more satisfactory and at the same time more sensitive to determine these ions by titrating the iodate formed in the reaction. Recently it has been found that periodate can be masked with molybdate² whereas iodate remains unaffected and can be determined iodometrically in a chloroacetic acid buffer of pH3. In the present communication this observation has been used for the development of a sensitive method for the estimation of sulphur compounds by titrating the iodate formed in the reaction.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade commercially available or prepared in the laboratory and purified by well known methods. Sodium or potassium salts were taken for the preparation of the solutions of the ions to be determined. Sulphite and bisulphite solutions were stabilized towards air oxidation by adding alcohol and standardised by iodine. Thiosulphate was standardised iodometrically in alkaline medium³. Strength of tri- and tetrathionates was determined by iodate⁴.

2 M molybdate solution was prepared by dissolving ammonium molybdate in hot distilled water.

Buffer solution was prepared by dissolving 25 g of chloroacetic acid in 70 ml water and its pH adjusted to 2.9 with strong sodium hydroxide solution.

Procedure: A suitable aliquot of the substance to be determined was pipetted into an erlenmeyer flask containing an excess of potassium metaperiodate (50-100 mg) and 10 ml of ~M/20 borax. The reaction mixture, except for sulphite and bisulphite determination, was boiled for 10 min and cooled to room temperature. 10-15 ml of 2M ammonium molybdate

followed by 10 ml of chloroacetic acid buffer and 1 g of potassium iodide were added and the iodine liberated was titrated with 0.1 N sodium thiosulphate. For sulphite and bisulphite determination, boiling was not necessary. However, the reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 2-3 min before the addition of ammonium molybdate. The amount of iodine liberated corresponded to the amount of ion taken for estimation. A blank of distilled water was taken through the whole process. The results are recorded in the Table.

TABLE—ESTIMATION OF SULPHIDE, HYDROSULPHIDE, SULPHITE, BISULPHITE, THIOSULPHATE, TRITHIONATE AND TETRATHIONATE.

Sulphide		Hydrosulphide	
Taken (mg)	Found (mg)	Taken (mg)	Found (mg)
1.56	1.55	1.38	1.38
1.83	1.83	1.53	1.51
2.20	2.18	1.84	1.82
2.57	2.59	2.10	2.09
3.12	3.12	2.76	2.75
3.90	3.91	3.45	3.45
Sulphite		Bisulphite	
10.65	10.73	10.79	10.80
14.20	14.20	14.38	14.45
17.75	17.67	18.43	18.36
23.30	23.27	22.11	22.07
28.40	28.27	28.96	28.96
35.50	35.60	35.94	36.11
Thiosulphate		Trithionate	
4.13	4.11	6.00	5.96
5.16	5.18	7.50	7.52
6.20	6.23	9.00	8.96
7.23	7.26	10.50	10.44
8.26	8.31	12.00	12.00
10.33	10.41	13.50	13.44
Tetrathionate			
	4.37	4.29	
	5.47	5.41	
	6.56	6.51	
	7.65	7.63	
	8.74	8.67	
	10.93	10.88	

Results and Discussion

In presence of borax, periodate oxidises the reducing ions under discussion quantitatively to sulphate and itself gets reduced to iodate. If the ions are represented by a general formula $H_xS_yO_z^{x-2}$, the reaction can be shown as

The iodate formed by periodate oxidation of the reducing ions (Eq. 1) has been determined by treating the products of the reaction with potassium iodide after masking of the excess of periodate with molybdate :

Since the amount of iodate formed in reaction (1) is stoichiometrically related to the amount of the ion taken for estimation, the production of iodine (Eq. 2) can be represented by :

The titration of the iodine produced makes the method highly sensitive. Even very small amounts of the ions can be accurately determined.

Nitrate, phosphate, acetate and arsenate do not interfere whereas chloride, bromide, formate, antimonate and oxalate interfere. However, chloride, bromide and formate do not interfere in the determination of sulphite and bisulphite.

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